

Portrayal of Disability in Media

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Abstract

The portrayal of any kind of disability in the media plays a significant role in molding the general public perception of disability. This article studies the representation of people with disabilities in popular media with special reference to Indian media. The mindset of the public towards disability and how the media can influence that is discussed. The implications of positive representations in media are also discussed.

Disability as Perceived by the Public

Disability can be any continuing condition that can include physical, psychological, sensory, emotional or cognitive impairment or a combination of any of these. The depiction of any kind of disability within the media plays a significant role in molding the general public perception of disability. Perceptions that appear in popular media directly influence how the people with disabilities are generally treated in current society. The media is an integral part of human life. Media platforms have been cited as a key site for the reinforcement of negative images and ideas in regard to people with disabilities (Hardin, 2001)

The media typically depicts individuals with disabilities in accordance to common stereotypes like pity and valour. Disability advocates usually refer to this social scenario as the “pity/heroism trap” or “pity/heroism dichotomy” (Ralston, 2009). Paul Hunt (1991) has identified 10 stereotypes that the media use to portray disabled people. These are, “The disabled person as pitiable or pathetic”, “An object of curiosity or violence”, “sinister or evil”, “the super cripple”, “as atmosphere”, “laughable”, “his/her own worst enemy”, “as a burden”, “as non-sexual” and “being unable to participate in daily life”

Negative day-to-day reporting may occur chiefly by depicting a given person or people with a disability as a burden or drain on society (Barnes, 2017). There are different models that are used in describing disability in the media. The “super-crip” model, in which subjects are portrayed as heroically overcoming their afflictions, is also often used when reporting on people with disabilities. The social model tends to be used for reporting on the activities of disability rights activists if the report is positive (Johnson, 2017). The media throughout history has pictured incapacity through the utilization of impairment. The media has focused on portraying impairment through the influence of the medical model of disability (Murada,2012).

When we mention the term media, we mean to include television, movies, radio, magazines, newspapers, the Internet, social media and other forms. All these forms of media play an important role in influencing public opinion and attitudes about disability. The way of explaining, usage of disability related terms, images and messages can influence attitudes and behaviours of the general public. It may also outline what will or will not influence people and also the world around them.

How people with disabilities are depicted in media and also the frequency with that they appear in the media has a colossal impact on however they will be regarded in society. Eventhough there may be disability-specific media programmes, such as television documentaries, disabled people rarely appear as part of mainstream programmes. When they are shown on media, they are often stigmatized or stereotyped, and may appear as either objects of pity or super heroic accomplishment and endurance.

Helping for their inclusion in regular programmes on television and radio in addition to other types of media can help provide fair and balanced representation and helps to counter commonplace stereotypes that perpetuate negative perceptions of disabled persons. Portraying individuals with disabilities with dignity and respect within the media will definitely facilitate promote more tolerant and inclusive societies. This is important because people with disabilities make up approximately 10 per cent of the global population. As a group, they may often be subject to discrimination or exclusion from basic services such as health, education, training and work opportunities. This leaves many disabled people and their families among the world’s poorest and most marginalized populations.

Second, in several countries, disabled persons often lack access to information about policies, laws and improvements in programmes and services that directly affect them. This knowledge gap perpetuates their exclusion from social, economic and political life. Promoting the inclusion of people with disabilities needs the support of all people as full members of society and readiness to respect of all their rights. Inclusion conjointly involves guaranteeing the participation of individuals with disabilities in most of the basic services offered to the overall population and also the removal of barriers – physical, attitudinal, legal, regulatory, policy, communication – that thwart them from working together in society.

How the media portray disability can help increase awareness throughout society about the realities faced by disabled persons, reduce stereotypes, prejudices and harmful practices, and promote awareness of their capabilities and contributions. When (peak versus non – peak times), how and how often disability is presented and the language used can nurture positive perceptions, foster respect for the rights and dignity of persons with disabilities and promote inclusive societies.

Representation of Disability in Media

There are many TV shows that have spoken about disability. Satyamev Jayate by Aamir Khan pointed out the problems faced by the individuals with disability. Channels like Doordarshan and Puthiya Thalamurai have news in sign language which helps in inclusion of individuals with hearing loss. Reality shows like Indian Idol Junior and Star Singer have had participants with disability. Seeing the individuals with disability performing on stage can be a motivating factor for the many disabled viewers. Movies that deal with disability or disabled people are common in most of the Indian regional languages. Some of the examples are Peranbu, Daivathirumakal, Haridas, Maa in Tamil; Black, Taare Zameen Par, Paa, My Name is Khan, Barfi, Kaabil, Fanaa in Hindi; Beautiful, Meerayude Dukhavum Muthuvinte Swapnavum, Albuthadweepu in Malayalam to name a few. How can the media support positive portrayal of disability and persons with disabilities

The Convention on the Rights of Disabled People recommends bringing awareness on disability to the public (United Nations, 2007). The media should raise awareness of the challenges facing

people with disabilities and issues surrounding disability, and factors that contribute to the problem and that can lead to stigmatization of people with disabilities. Bringing discussion about persons with disability into common conversation to challenge the concept of it as a taboo subject is useful. The popular media should feature people with disabilities as sources of support for their families and communities and as people with experience, services and assistance.

There has to be more valid and meaningful discussions about the exclusion of persons with disability from general social, economic and political life and overcome lack of access to most areas of development, including health, education, food, shelter, employment and land. The media should also promote policies, products, services and environments that support the full participation and development of all people, including disabled people. The media should also disseminate the contact information of various governmental and non-governmental support services.

Printed media can include applicable sources of support at the top of an editorial or a programme to assist make sure that persons with disabilities and their families get the knowledge they have, as well as facts about improvements in national policies and programmes. Moreover the media should promote the message that individuals with disabilities are a gift in each community and they too can actively contribute to the society if they are given an opportunity. Persons with disability should be portrayed as having the same complexity of personality and experience as others.

Implications

The disabled continue to suffer in varied manners even though the media have been representing their issues for amicable solutions. Since the media and society are interdependent on each other, problems in representing the disabled, causes a ripple effect in the society. There is no doubt that media and the information it portrays plays a very important role in modern human life. Moreover, the Information Technology (IT) possesses the power to shape up the individual and collective life of a given society. The difference of accessibility between two communities creates the state of digital divide. In the light of issues of the disabled, the mainstream debate has failed to address adequately their information accessibility issues (Chaudhry & Shipp, 2005).

The issue of technological inaccessibility for the disabled has remained low profile discussion in the discipline of communication. As a result, they have been subjected to deprivations in terms of information needs. Since the disabled is not mainstreamed, it creates an invisible state of minority in social, cultural and economic spheres. As a result, they are yet to be in the process of inclusive development. Moreover, the marginalisation is greater to the visually impaired persons. The state known as ‘_Digital Disability’ is often criticised (Goggin and Newell, 2003). Here, technologies have become liabilities instead of assets for them due to inaccessibility issues.

The rapid technological innovations have provided impetus to social, economic and cultural arena. Information technology as an agent of boosting growth at global level, has accepted at all the levels. However, to some, the advent of information technology has intensified the magnitude of digital divide (Chaudhry & Shipp, 2005). Since the disabled are lagging behind in applying the basic and existing technological tools, information revolution has proved disadvantages for them, especially for the visually-impaired persons. The more is the momentum in technological advancements, the more is the gap between the disabled and non-disabled society. (Goggin & Newell, 2003, Warshauer, 2003).

The state of information inequality has led to the broader issue of under-representation and under-participation of the disabled in the process of production and distribution of information. However, some argue that the use of video and animation in the World Wide Web can resolve the complex issues and can make the technologies disabled-friendly (Ellis & Kent, 2010). In fact, managing their e-space inclusion is not an easy task. So, it is imperative to understand the interplay of disability,

information technology, political economy, social and cultural parameters. The inequality in the domain of communication pertaining to under-representation and misrepresentation of the disabled has paved the way to look for and consider the alternative media.

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